

Can Bell's formulation in his paper "Bertlmann's socks and the nature of reality" lead to an undecidable problem?

Alexandre de Castro*
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Here it is shown a problem of undecidability in the formulation used in [J.S. Bell, Bertlmann's socks and the nature of reality, CERN Ref.TH.2926- CERN (1980)] which makes the Bell inequality tests inconclusive.

Keywords: Born rule; Bell inequality test; Kolmogorov's axioms.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we examine a potential undecidability issue arising from Bell's formulation in "Bertlmann's Socks and the Nature of Reality" [1]. By analyzing probability distributions in a Hilbert space formalism, we identify a logical impasse that questions whether Bell's inequality tests can be conclusively interpreted as evidence for quantum nonlocality. This result has potential implications not only for the interpretation of Bell experiments but also for a broader applicability of quantum probability theory. If the undecidability issue holds, it may necessitate a reassessment of the foundational assumptions underlying Bell's theorem and its role in quantum information science.

II. PRELIMINARIES

In ref.[1]/pg.(9), consider Ineq.(9): "The probability of being able to pass at 0.0° and not able at $90.0^\circ \leq$ The probability of being able to pass 0.0° and not able at $45.0^\circ +$ The probability of being able to pass at 45.0° and not able at 90.0° "

This inequality can be written as:

$$P[a+, b-] \leq P[a+, c-] + P[b-, c+], \quad (1)$$

where $a = 0.0^\circ$, $b = 90.0^\circ$, $c = 45.0^\circ$ and \pm corresponds to "able to pass" and "not able", respectively.

Let's represent the events as orthonormal vectors in an inner product space: We can write the following operation defined upon the vector space:

$$\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle = \begin{cases} \langle b- | a+ \rangle = \cos(45.0^\circ + 90^\circ) = -\sin 45.0^\circ \\ \langle c- | a+ \rangle = \cos(22.5^\circ + 90^\circ) = -\sin 22.5^\circ \\ \langle c+ | b- \rangle = \cos(22.5^\circ + 90^\circ) = -\sin 22.5^\circ \end{cases}$$

By the Born rule, the modulus-squared of $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$ results:

$$P[\cdot, \cdot] = \begin{cases} P[a+, b-] = |\langle b- | a+ \rangle|^2 = \sin^2 45.0^\circ \\ P[a+, c-] = |\langle c- | a+ \rangle|^2 = \sin^2 22.5^\circ \\ P[b-, c+] = |\langle c+ | b- \rangle|^2 = \sin^2 22.5^\circ \end{cases}$$

FIG. 1. Vector space together with an inner product $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$ on it, such that $\theta = 45.0^\circ$

Thus, Ineq.(1) requires:

$$\sin^2 45.0^\circ \leq 2 \sin^2 22.5^\circ, \quad (2)$$

in accordance with pg.(10) in ref.[1]. This result claims that the probability $P[a+, b-]$ obtained by applying the Born rule is not compatible with the local model of probability distribution (1) derived from the Kolmogorov's axioms (see Appendix).

III. UNDECIDABILITY

The Born rule requires $P[a+, b-] \in [0, 1]$, once $P[a+, b-]$ is a sine-squared function This numeric bound, $0 \leq P[a+, b-] \leq 1$, is equivalent to the inequality:

$$P[a+, b-] \leq \sqrt{P[a+, b-]}, \quad (3)$$

because one is the solution set of the other.

From which,

$$P[a+, b-] \leq \sqrt{|\langle b- | a+ \rangle|^2}, \quad (4)$$

id est, $P[a+, b-]$ is less than or equal to the modulus of its probability amplitude.

Hence,

$$P[a+, b-] \leq \sqrt{|-\sin 45.0^\circ|^2}, \quad (5)$$

* Embrapa; alexandre.castro@embrapa.br

Then one can rewrite this last inequality (5) as:

$$1 - \sin^2 45.0^\circ \leq \sin 45.0^\circ, \quad (6)$$

or even as:

$$1 - \sin 45.0^\circ \leq \sin^2 45.0^\circ. \quad (7)$$

And making use of the trigonometric identity:

$$1 - \sin 45.0^\circ = 2 \sin^2 22.5^\circ, \quad (8)$$

we then obtain:

$$2 \sin^2 22.5^\circ \leq \sin^2 45.0^\circ, \quad (9)$$

which is a result opposite to [2].

IV. LOGICAL CONSEQUENCE

Taking into account that the inequalities (2) and (9) are both derived from the same formulation, then an logical impasse is generated. Faced to this, we cannot decide whether or not the probability $P[a+, b-]$ obtained by applying the Born rule is compatible with the local model

of probability distribution (1). This trouble touches the Bell tests [1], since from $CHSH > 2$, no inference can be validated.

V. APPENDIX

Derivation of the local model of probability distribution (1) from Kolmogorov's axioms. Consider the probability experiment of tossing three coins simultaneously, so that the throws (a, b, c) are independent of each other. In such condition, there are $2^3 = 8$ mutually exclusive events:

Throws/Outcomes			First axiom ↓
a	b	c	$P_i \geq 0$
H	H	H	1/8
H	H	T	1/8
H	T	H	1/8
H	T	T	1/8
T	H	H	1/8
T	H	T	1/8
T	T	H	1/8
T	T	T	1/8
Second axiom →			$\sum P_i = 1$

where H and T represent head and tail, respectively.

Notably, the probabilities of occurring the disjoint events $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [HT(H \vee T)] \\ [H(H \vee T)T] \\ [(H \vee T)TH] \end{array} \right.$

are as follows (Third axiom):

$$\begin{aligned} P[HT(H \vee T)] &= P[HTH] + P[H TT] - P[HTH \wedge H TT] = \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8} = \frac{1}{4} \\ P[H(H \vee T)T] &= P[HHT] + P[H TT] - P[HHT \wedge H TT] = \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8} = \frac{1}{4} \\ P[(H \vee T)TH] &= P[HTH] + P[TTH] - P[HTH \wedge TTH] = \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8} = \frac{1}{4} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

given that $P[HTH \wedge H TT] = P[HHT \wedge H TT] = P[HTH \wedge TTH] = 0$ for mutually exclusive events.

Thus, combining the inequations (10), stays:

$$P[HT(H \vee T)] \leq P[H(H \vee T)T] + P[(H \vee T)TH] \quad (11)$$

which is a basic result of Kolmogorov's probability theory. In other words, the probability that the first coin (flipping a) lands on head, the second coin (flipping b) lands on tail and the third coin (flipping c) lands whatever outcome is less than or equal to the probability that the first coin (flipping a) lands on head, the second coin

(flipping b) lands whatever outcome and the third coin (flipping c) lands tail plus the probability that the first coin (flipping a) lands whatever outcome, the second coin (flipping b) lands on tail and the third coin (flipping c) lands on head.

As the logical disjunction $(H \vee T)$ doesn't matter, then the above inequality (11) can be written in the form (1): $P[a+, b-] \leq P[a+, c-] + P[b-, c+]$, where “+” and “-” corresponds to H and T , respectively.

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- [1] J.S. Bell, Bertlmann's socks and the nature of reality,
CERN Ref.TH.2926- CERN (1980)